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Sandwich panels for high-performance model aircraft: a case study

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Abstract: This work describes a sandwich composite designed for a model aircraft under Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) competition. A Design of Experiment (DoE) is used to investigate the flexural properties of four sandwich panels consisting of two types of skins, made of laminated composites (carbon or glass), and two types of cores (balsa wood or expanded polystyrene). Absolute and specific properties are evaluated from a mechanical performance perspective, providing valuable information to maximise aircraft structure. Sandwich panels achieve acceptable properties for application in aero design structures, combining stiffness and lightness. Panels composed of carbon skins and balsa wood provide greater specific strength and stiffness, being used as a structural material for the "*Trem Ki Voa*" aeroplane at the Federal University of São João del-Rei (UFSJ-Brazil).

1. Introduction

The aircraft and drone industries have been working on different material solutions to maximise the performance of their products, especially considering the use of composite materials, which combines high stiffness and low weight [1]. Sandwich panels have low density and high rigidity, being a promising structural material for parts of the project and in general have been studied since 1930s in civil and military applications [2]. The effective properties of sandwich panels depend on a thin, dense and strong skin bonded to a thick, lightweight core material, but especially on their geometry, affecting the area's moment of inertia [3], [4].

The Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) annually organises a model aircraft competition, supported by Embraer, covering several teams among Brazilian undergraduate courses. The Federal University of São João del-

Rei (USFJ, Brazil) has participated in this competition since 2000 with the "Trem Ki Voa" team. Sandwich panels were chosen as the structural material to manufacture the model airplane for the 2017 SAE competition.

In this context, this work presents the characterisation of different sandwich panels under three-point bending. A full factorial design 2^2 has been performed to identify the effects of two composite skins (carbon or glass fibre reinforced polymer) and two core materials (balsa wood or Styrofoam) on the absolute and specific flexural properties of the sandwich panels.

2. Methodology

2.1. Fabrication and mechanical characterisation

As shown in Fig. 1 (a), two laminated composite skins composed of carbon or glass fibres and two core types, balsa wood and Styrofoam, are used. A cross-ply carbon fibre fabric (RC203P, 12k weft) with 193 g/m² grammage is used. Glass fibre (RE200P) is a cross-ply fabric of 200 g/m² grammage. Both fabrics and balsa wood are sourced from Barracuda Advanced Composites (Brazil). Balsa wood has approximately 150 kg/m³ in density and 5 mm in thickness, while Styrofoam is about 23 kg/m³ and 5 mm in thickness. The epoxy system composed of RenLam[®] M resin and Aradur[®] HY956-2 catalyst is used as the matrix phase, combining low viscosity, high adhesion and room temperature cure. According to the Huntsman datasheet, the mixture is prepared in a 100:20 ratio (resin/catalyst).

A hand lay-up technique is used for lamination of the specimens, considering a 70% matrix volume fraction. After seven days of curing, the laminates are cut and bonded to the core material following the dimensions (200 x 75 mm²) indicated in ASTM C393/C393M. Four samples are made for each experimental condition, considering two replicates, totalling eight tests. A cold press of approximately 600 kPa is used to bond the skins to the core by the same epoxy system used in the lamination, providing panels with a total thickness of about 5.61 mm. A 100 kN Shimadzu AG-X Plus testing machine performs three-point bending with a span length of 150 mm and a crosshead speed of 1.5 mm/min – Fig. 1 (b). The ratio between mass and volume measures the equivalent density of the panels. The specific properties are obtained by dividing the mechanical properties by the equivalent density.

Fig. 1. Assessed sandwich panels (a) and three-point bending test (b).

2.2. Statistical approach

All possible combinations should be tested under a full factorial design to determine the influence of each factor and their interactions on the responses [5]. A full factorial design of 2^2 corresponds to two factors tested at two different levels, leading to four experimental conditions. Table 1 shows the Design of Experiment (DoE)

performed, considering two factors, such as the skin and core materials, and their respective levels: fibre and carbon composites for the skin factor; balsa wood and Styrofoam for the core factor. All statistical manipulation is performed using Minitab® Software [6].

Table 1. Full factorial design.

Conditions	Skin	Core
1 - CB	carbon fibre	balsa wood
2 - CS	carbon fibre	Styrofoam
3 - GB	glass fibre	balsa wood
4 - GS	glass fibre	Styrofoam

3. Results and Discussions

Table 2 shows the mean data obtained for Replicate 1 and 2, and Table 3 shows the DoE model data. The results are interpreted via effect plots obtained from the DoE analysis. The main factors are only analysed individually when their interaction is not significant.

Table 2. Mean properties for replicate 1 and 2.

Setup	ρ		σ_{\max}	\check{E}^*	σ_{\max}^*	
	g/cm ³	GPa	MPa	GPa.cm ³ /g	MPa.cm ³ /g	
Replicate 1	GB	0.260	3.779	12.017	14.535	46.219
	GS	0.230	1.589	4.373	6.908	19.014
	CB	0.304	8.458	17.056	27.825	56.115
	CS	0.277	3.003	7.251	10.834	26.155
Replicate 2	GB	0.273	3.763	11.695	13.771	42.792
	GS	0.243	1.843	4.574	7.583	18.823
	CB	0.304	8.463	15.762	27.864	51.897
	CS	0.265	2.863	6.702	10.818	25.323

ρ is the equivalent density; \check{E} is the flexural modulus; σ_{\max} is the flexural strength; * indicates specific properties.

The flexural modulus measured in this work is the “slope flexural modulus”, according to the approach presented in the RJS Method [7], i.e., the slope of the straight-line portion of the stress-strain curve. The method states that, for small specimens, the “slope flexural modulus” is underestimated in relation to the “real flexural modulus”, which can be measured for specimens with structural dimensions (high panel width and support span length in relation to the panel thickness). The core rigidity has more influence on the slope flexural modulus when

the specimens are smaller, since the smaller the specimen, the more the flexural modulus tends to approach the core flexural modulus. The RJS Method still assumes that the final application of the panels must be taken into account when realising a flexural test to obtain a real prediction of mean stress and strain behaviour on the elastic regime. As the present work aims to apply panels with small dimensions (model aircraft), the characterisation of small specimens for obtaining the “slope flexural modulus” is valid.

Table 3. DoE model analysis.

Assumptions under verification: residuals are normally distributed and have equal variances.

	ρ	$\bar{\epsilon}$	σ_{max}	$\bar{\epsilon}^*$	σ_{max}^*
R^2	94.77%	99.92%	99.37%	99.89%	99.06%
R^2 (adj)	90.85%	99.86%	98.91%	99.81%	98.35%
R^2 (pred)	79.08%	99.68%	97.50%	99.57%	96.22%
P-Value ^{AD (RESI)}	0.075	0.510	0.932	0.210	0.721
P-Value ^{B (RESI)}	0.179	0.071	0.465	0.056	0.209
P-Value ^{Face}	0.003	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.004
P-Value ^{Core}	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
P-Value ^{Int.}	0.818	0.000	0.048	0.000	0.385

R^2 determine how well the model fits the data; R^2 (adj) is the percentage of the variation in the responses that is explained by the model; R^2 (pred) determine how well the model predicts the responses for new observations; P-Value^{AD (RESI)} is the Anderson Darling test of residuals and values greater than 0.05 indicate normal distribution; P-Value^{B (RESI)} is the Barlett’s test of residuals and values greater than 0.05 indicate homogeneity of variances; P-Value^{Face}, P-Value^{Core}, and P-Value^{Int.} indicate, respectively, if the Face Type factor, Core Type factor and the Interaction of factors have influence on responses, and values lesser than 0.05 indicate significant influence.

Figure 2 shows the main effects plot for the fitted means of equivalent density. A lower density is obtained for those panels manufactured with glass fibre composite skins and Styrofoam core. Although carbon fibres are less dense than glass fibres, it should be noted that fabrics of similar grammage are used, therefore carbon fabrics are thicker than glass fabrics, which explains the higher density of panels with laminated carbon fibre skins.

Fig. 2. Main effects plot for the fitted means of equivalent density.

The fitted means of slope flexural modulus and flexural strength data range from 1.72 to 8.41 GPa and 4.47 to 16.41 MPa, respectively. Figure 3 shows the effects interaction plots for the slope flexural modulus (a) and flexural strength (b). The graphs exhibit similar behaviour. When combined carbon fibre composite skins and balsa wood, greater strength and stiffness (high flexural modulus) are achieved. The Styrofoam core leads to a substantial reduction in mechanical performance. Such behaviour can be attributed to the skin's poor physical adhesion to the Styrofoam surface. The flexural strength of panels with carbon fibre composite skins is nearly 21.54% higher than those composed of glass fibre skins, especially considering a wood core. The balsa wood core leads to up to 186.60% greater slope flexural modulus than Styrofoam core when combined with carbon fibre skins, according to the RJS Method [7], evidencing that for small samples, the core rigidity has a great influence on the panel stiffness.

Fig. 3. Interaction effects for the fitted means of (a) slope flexural modulus and (b) flexural strength.

Figure 4 shows the effects interaction plot for the specific slope flexural modulus (a) and the main effects plot for the specific flexural strength (b). The plots are pretty similar to the absolute responses; however, a slight percent variation increase is evidenced between carbon fibre skin panels made with balsa and Styrofoam for the specific flexural strength. Although Styrofoam contributes to reducing the total weight of the panels, balsa wood core provides a substantial mechanical contribution, leading to enhanced specific properties. As known, carbon fibre composite skins also corroborate to obtain high rigid and lightweight structure.

Fig. 4. Interaction effects (a) for the fitted means of specific slope flexural modulus and main effects (b) for the fitted means of specific flexural strength.

4. Conclusions

While balsa wood and carbon fibre have increased the panels' equivalent density, their superior mechanical performance led to enhanced specific properties. Furthermore, absolute superior properties have been achieved by carbon fibre-balsa wood panels. The substantial reduction in flexural properties achieved by Styrofoam cores can be attributed to their lower adhesion to composite skins and the great influence of core rigidity on the stiffness of small-sized panels under flexural loading. Finally, sandwich panels made of carbon fibre skins and wooden cores were used to manufacture the model aeroplane designed by the *Trem Ki Voa* team used in the SAE 2017 competition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

CRediT author statement

E.D. Vial: Conceptualisation; Methodology; Investigation; Data Curation; Validation; Writing – Original Draft; Writing – Review & Editing. **R.J. da Silva:** Validation; Formal analysis; Visualisation; Writing – Review & Editing. **T.H. Panzera:** Conceptualisation; Validation; Resources; Supervision; Writing – Review & Editing. **M. L. P. Tonatto:** Conceptualisation. **G. B. de Magalhães Santos:** Conceptualisation.

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